

EAA 2020

VIRTUAL

24-30 August

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**26th EAA
Annual Meeting
Scientific Programme**

26th Annual Meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists - Scientific Programme

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503 GENERAL SESSION - HUMAN-ANIMAL RELATIONSHIPS

Date: Sunday 30 August
Time: 9:00 - 12:00 CEST
Theme: 5. Theories and methods in archaeology: interactions between disciplines
Format: Regular session
Chair: Bartosiewicz, László (Stockholm University)

ABSTRACTS

- 9:00 **INTERDISCIPLINARITY TO AID ARCHAEOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF ANIMALS IN EGYPT AND NEAR EAST**
Gransard-Desmond, Jean-Olivier (ArkéoTopia, une autre voie pour l'archéologie)
- 9:15 **ORNITHOMORPHIC IMAGES IN THE UPPER PALEOLITHIC (MAL'TA BURET' CULTURE, SIBERIA)**
Pankina, Anna - Lbova, Liudmila - Kazakov, Vladislav (Novosibirsk State University)
- 9:30 **THE PATHWAYS OF HUMANS AND ANIMALS IN THE EARLY NEOLITHIC BALKANS: AN ARCHAEOZOOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE**
Zivaljevic, Ivana (BioSense Institute, University of Novi Sad) - Dimitrijević, Vesna (Laboratory for Bioarchaeology, Department of Archaeology, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade; BioSense Institute, University of Novi Sad) - Stefanović, Sofija (BioSense Institute, University of Novi Sad; Laboratory for Bioarchaeology, Department of Archaeology, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade)
- 9:45 **DISCUSSION SLOT**
- 10:00 **SPATIAL BEHAVIOR OF MAMMOTH HUNTERS OF EPIGRAVETTIAN MEZHRYCH CULTURE IN MIDDLE DNIEPER BASIN (UKRAINE)**
Shydlovskiy, Pavlo (Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv; Center for Paleoethnological Research) - Péan, Stéphane (Muséum national d'histoire naturelle, Paris) - Tsvirkun, Ostap (Institute of Archaeology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine; Center for Paleoethnological Research) - Chymyrys, Marharyta (Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv; Center for Paleoethnological Research) - Mamchur, Bohdan (University of Ferrara, Italy; Center for Paleoethnological Research)
- 10:15 **NON-ECONOMIC USE OF ANIMALS IN THE EARLY IRON AGE CENTRAL BALKANS: THE CASE OF THE ŠLJUNKARA – ZEMUN SETTLEMENT**
Bulatovic, Jelena (Laboratory for Bioarchaeology, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade) - Spasic, Milos (Pre-historic Collection, Department of Archaeology, Belgrade City Museum)
- 10:30 **HUNTING FOR THE MYCENAEANS**
Georgiadis, Mercurios (Institute of Classical Archaeology in Catalunya)
- 10:45 **DISCUSSION SLOT**

POSTERS

- A. **STUDY OF THE IDENTITY OF A BRETON MAMMOTH FROM ATTENED TUSK PIECES TOMOGRAPHY**
Barreau, Jean-Baptiste - Le Maire, Mikaël (Univ Rennes, CNRS, CReAAH UMR 6566, Rennes) - Bourbouze, Gaël (CRT Morlaix)

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Abstract Book

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ORGANISER

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The Abstract Book is ordered by session numbers which were allocated during the session submission (i.e., the number sequence is discontinuous).

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Index of Authors includes all session organisers and only the main authors of contributions.

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503 **GENERAL SESSION - HUMAN-ANIMAL RELATIONSHIPS**

Theme: 5. Theories and methods in archaeology: interactions between disciplines

Chair: Bartosiewicz, László (Stockholm University)

Format: Regular session

ABSTRACTS

4 SPATIAL BEHAVIOR OF MAMMOTH HUNTERS OF EPIGRAVETTIAN MEZHRYCH CULTURE IN MIDDLE DNEIPER BASIN (UKRAINE)

Author(s): Shydlovskiy, Pavlo (Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine; Center for Paleoethnological Research) - Péan, Stéphane (Muséum national d'histoire naturelle, Paris) - Tsvirkun, Ostap (Institute of Archaeology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine; Center for Paleoethnological Research) - Chymyrys, Marharyta (Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv; Center for Paleoethnological Research) - Mamchur, Bohdan (University of Ferrara; Center for Paleoethnological Research)

Format: Oral

In recent years, the Epigravettian site of Mezhyrich in the Middle Dnieper region, has been continuously studied, including the fourth mammoth bone dwelling, which was discovered in 1978 and left in situ for future research.

The complexity of the dwelling cultural layer reveals several surfaces of residence; in addition, a functional specialisation of areas and objects within the dwelling, associated with the processing of flint, animal bones and skins has been identified. The structural features of the building are characterized by symmetry and rhythmicity in the use of large mammoth bones, which makes up the basement of structure, exterior cladding and upper roof overlap that fell inside. The archaeological structures around the dwelling have different economic specificities (processing areas, workshops, pits, outer hearths, areas of a rich cultural layer). In total, four units each one being composed of a central dwelling have been discovered since the site was opened.

In addition to the base camps with mammoth bone architecture (Mezhyrich, Gontsy, Dobranichivka), a number of short-term sites, kill-sites and localities of Late Pleistocene fauna have been investigated in the Middle Dnieper. The technological analysis, together with the radiocarbon data, show that the sites of the so-called "Mezhyrichian culture" are the remnants of the activity of a single society that lived in a rather limited territory 15-14 ka 14C BP. This conclusion provides a unique opportunity to reconstruct some

features of spatial behaviour of the hunting groups, which had a centralized logistic character. Base camps were arranged in the centre of the seasonal movements of the group, in the most convenient places.

The current level of study of Epigravettian sites of the Middle Dnieper basin allows to create a model of settlement patterns of Upper Palaeolithic human groups and to reconstruct several levels of use of the surrounding space.